

Lived Experiences of Senior High School Students with English as a Third Language (E3L)

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ABSTRACT

This study focused on exploring the lived experiences of students with E3L in the Philippines, considering the specific context on investigating the challenges encountered in communicating with their classmates and determining how their first language or mother tongue affect language use and understanding. In this phenomenological qualitative research, the purposive sampling design was utilized. As per Bekele and Ago (2022), phenomenological research is a strategy of inquiry in which the researcher identifies the essence of human experiences about a phenomenon as described by participants. In this process, the researcher brackets or sets aside his or her own experiences to understand those of the participants in the study. This study required four (4) participants that comprised senior high school senior high school students in Mamatid Senior High School with English as

a third language (E3L). Creswell (2013) suggested that a reasonable sample size may range from 3 -25 participants for a phenomenological study. Based on the testimonies gathered from the participants, they unveiled 39 subordinate themes, 10 superordinate themes, and five (5) main themes. Particularly, these main themes were: (1) Primary Language and Communication Environment; (2) Negative Effects of Mother Tongue; (3) Adaptation and Integration of Media; (4) Supportive Learning Environment; and (5) Language Skill Development. As a result, the researcher produced a Holistic Language Skill Development Plan that incorporates (1) English and Filipino Programs, (2) Integration of Language Education in Home Room Guidance, (3) Utilization of English and Filipino language and Translanguaging, (4) Emphasis on Easy-to-pronounce Words, and (5) Home Support for the Senior High School Students.

Keywords: *English as a third language (E3L), English, Filipino, mother tongue, translanguaging*

INTRODUCTION

The Philippines has a rich linguistic landscape with numerous regional languages and dialects. Filipino, based on Tagalog, serves as the national language. However, English holds a significant position in education, government, and business. This creates a situation where many Filipino senior high school students encounter English as their third language, after their native language and Filipino.

According to UNESCO, 221 million children worldwide are estimated to speak a different language at home from the language of instruction in their school.¹ This mismatch may create inequalities in access to learning in early childhood, stigma, and marginalization. An increasing number of countries in Asia have started to implement native language-based multilingual education policies to address these issues.

The Philippine Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) was initiated in the 2012-2013 school year as part of the Department of Education's Enhanced Basic Education Program initiatives, shifting schools' language of instruction from a bilingual system of English and Filipino to students' local mother tongue. Under this policy, senior high school students learn basic numeracy and literacy skills in their mother tongue from kindergarten to Grade 3 before switching back to the "dominant" languages from Grade 4 onwards. Because the Philippines is a linguistically diverse country—with over 100 languages—a total of 19 languages are recognized under the MTB-MLE policy implemented by the Department of Education.

Accordingly, as per Executive Order No. 210, Establishing the Policy to Strengthen the Use of the English Language as a Medium of Instruction in the Educational System, whereas, Section 7, Article XIV of the 1987 Constitution provides that for purposes of communication and instruction, the official languages of the Philippines are Filipino and, until otherwise provided by law, English. The following policies are hereby established:

First, English shall be taught as a second language, starting with the First Grade; second, as provided for in the 2002 Basic Education Curriculum, English shall be used as the medium of instruction for English, Mathematics and Science from at least the Third Grade level; and third, the English language shall be used as the primary medium of instruction in all public and private institutions of learning in the secondary level, including those established as laboratory and/or experimental schools, and non-formal and vocational or technical educational institutions. As the primary medium of instruction, the percentage of time allotment for learning areas conducted in the English language is expected to be not less than seventy percent (70%) of the total time allotment for all learning areas in the secondary level.

This research aimed to explore the lived experiences of Students with E3L in the Philippines, considering the specific context on investigating the challenges encountered in communicating with their classmates and determining how their first language or mother tongue affect language use and understanding.

METHODS

In this phenomenological qualitative research, the purposive sampling design was utilized. As per Bekele and Ago (2022), phenomenological research is a strategy of inquiry in which the researcher identifies the essence of human experiences about a phenomenon as described by participants. Understanding the lived experiences marks phenomenology as a philosophy as well as a method, and the procedure involves studying a small number of subjects through extensive and prolonged engagement to develop patterns and relationships of meaning. In this process, the researcher brackets or sets aside his or her own experiences to understand those of the participants in the study. With these, the researcher came up with the following research questions:

Main Question:

What is the essence of the lived experience of senior high school students with English as a third language (E3L) in Mamatid Senior High School?

Corollary Questions

1. How do the senior high school students with English as a third language (E3L) in Mamatid Senior High School describe their experience?
2. What are the emerging themes based on the gathered data?
3. Based on the findings of the study, what Holistic Language Skill Development Plan may be proposed?

Accordingly, the participants who met the eligibility criteria were communicated, and the purpose of the study was explained in the consent letter and before the start of the interview. This study required four (4) participants that comprised senior high school senior high school students in Mamatid Senior High School with

English as a third language (E3L). Creswell (2013) suggested that a reasonable sample size may range from 3 -25 participants for a phenomenological study.

The following were the selection criteria for the participants of the study: (1) senior high school student in Mamatid Senior High School in academic year 2022 to 2023; and (2) uses English as third language.

In gathering pertinent information, the researcher utilized a semi-structured interview with 10 interview guide questions which combines a pre-determined set of open questions (questions that prompt discussion) with the opportunity for the researcher to explore particular themes or responses further. After that, the crafted questions were validated by three (3) language experts which served as the researcher's colleagues and attained master's degree units.

All the suggestions and corrections were applied and modified to improve the questions. The improved questions were revalidated and were used for the interview.

After that, ten (10) interview guide questions were asked to the participants to delve more into their relevant experiences about the research topic.

1. Can you tell me a bit about your language background? What languages do you speak at home and in your community?
2. How did you first start learning English? Can you describe your early experiences learning English?
3. What are some of the advantages of being an E3L student in the Philippines?
4. What are some of the disadvantages of being an E3L student in the Philippines?
5. Have you ever felt embarrassed or discouraged when using English in the classroom? If so, can you tell me about an example?
6. How do you think factors like dialects, accents, and cultural backgrounds affect classroom communication for Students with E3L?
7. What strategies do you use to overcome challenges in understanding and using English in the classroom?
8. Do you have any specific resources or support systems that help you learn English?
9. How do you feel teachers can better support Students with E3L in the classroom?
10. Looking ahead, what are some of your goals for improving your English language skills?

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Corollary Question 1. How do the senior high school students with English as a third language (E3L) in Mamatid Senior High School describe their experience?

Can you tell me a bit about your language background? What languages do you speak at home and in your community?

Table 1.1 *Annotated Exemplars on Languages Spoken at Home and Community*

Participant	Responses	Observation
SHS 1	Ang una ko pong language ay Chavacano. Nu'ng bata pa po ako sa lugar namin, Zamboanga. Mas kinakasanayan ko po ang language namin dahil ito po ang gamit namin sa bahay, sa labas ng bahay. Sa loob ng school, Tagalog po ang gamit namin.	With a normal tone of voice, SHS 1 seemed confident in uttering her responses.

Regarding the languages that the SHS students speak at home and in their community, SHS 1 seemed confident in uttering her responses. It implies that she knows what she is sharing about the way she communicates, specifically in using her mother tongue.

How did you first start learning English? Can you describe your early experiences learning English?

Table 1.2 Annotated Exemplars on Early Experiences in Learning English

Participant	Responses	Observation
SHS 1	Natuto na po ako talaga mag-English sa pagsasalita dito na po sa Laguna nu'ng Grade 10 po ako kasi karamihan po sa mga teachers po naming kailangan po naming mag-participate gamit ang English. Nag-eenglish po kami sa Zamboanga pero mas Tagalog po ang ginagamit namin sa pag-aaral.	SHS 1 expressed her answer with enthusiastic voice while maintaining eye contact.

With the participants' early experiences in learning English, SHS 1 exudes enthusiastic voice while maintaining eye contact. This implies that still, she narrates everything she experienced when she was younger. She mentioned there that it was acquired entirely when she was already in Grade 10.

What are some of the advantages of being a student with E3L in the Philippines?

Table 1.3 Annotated Exemplars on Advantages of Being a Student with E3L in the Philippines

Participant	Responses	Observation
SHS 2	Pwede po ako makipag-usap sa probinsya at dito po sa Laguna.	SHS 2 uttered her response with confident tone of voice while maintaining proper posture.

About the advantages in using English as a third language, SHS 2 expressed his responses with confidence. Just like in the preceding observations, this implies that he knows what he is narrating to the researcher. Since SHS 2 is one of the researcher's students, he seems comfortable in his narrations.

What are some of the disadvantages of being an E3L student in the Philippines?

Table 1.4 Annotated Exemplars on Advantages of Being a Student with E3L in the Philippines

Participant	Responses	Observation
SHS 2	Minsan hindi ako nakakasabay sa kanila dahil ang kanilang lenggwahe ay iba sa amin. Kaya nu'ng pinagbasa po ako nu'ng first semester, naiyak po dahil sa hiya. Kaya napaiyak po ako sa classroom.	With a low tone of voice, SHS 2 expressed his answer. He also exuded a frowning facial expression while narrating his experiences.

Regarding the advantages of being a student with E3L, SHS 2 expressed his answer with a frowning facial expression. This implies that this experience is unfavorable on his part as senior high school student. This makes him disappointed since he cannot cope with his classmates' progress in utilizing the language used in school.

Have you ever felt embarrassed or discouraged when using English in the classroom? If so, can you tell me about an example?

Table 1.5 Annotated Exemplars on Embarrassing and Discouraging Experiences when using English in the Classroom

Participant	Responses	Observation
SHS 1	'Pag ano po, kapag kinausap po ako ng kaklase ko ng English, hindi po ako makasagot, kasi hindi po ako masyado marunong.	SHS 1 expressed her responses with a low tone of voice.

Kapag nag-English po mga kaibigan ko, nag-uusap po kami, kapag ako na po ang magsasalita, magtatawanan po. Eh di ako po, minsan may doubt na po ako sa sarili ko, pinagtatawanan po ako, hindi ako kino-correct.

SHS 1 expressed her responses with a low tone of voice. Just like in question 5, she is also affected by the question as she narrates a negative experience in the classroom.

How do you think factors like dialects, accents, and cultural backgrounds affect classroom communication for students with E3L?

Table 1.6 *Annotated Exemplars on Factors Affecting Classroom Communication*

Participant	Responses	Observation
SHS 2	Kapag binubully po ako sa classroom sabay ano ang bilis ko po mapaiyak kapag sinasabing hindi ako marunong mag-English. Sa pagsasalita ko po kasi, bulol po ganoon, mahirap pong magsalita.	SHS 2 seemed so disappointed as he expressed his answer with sad tone of voice and facial expression.

SHS 2 seemed so disappointed as he expressed his answer with sad tone of voice and facial expression. This implies that he can clear remember the unfavorable experience of his in using the English language in the classroom. It makes him feel again the situation where he got so emotional and bullied by his classmates.

What strategies do you use to overcome challenges in understanding and using English in the classroom?

Table 1.7 *Annotated Exemplars on Overcoming Challenges on English in the Classroom*

Participant	Responses	Observation
SHS 1	Kapag dating ko po sa room po, nakikita ko po ang mga kaklase ko. Sinasabi ko po sa sarili ko na dapat matuto rin ako mag-English para makasabay ako sa kanila.	While maintaining an eye contact, SHS 1 expressed her responses.

While maintaining an eye contact, SHS 1 expressed her responses. This implies that still the participant is into the topic, she can clearly remember the things she has to do to continuously overcome challenges in using the English language.

8. Do you have any specific resources or support systems that help you learn English?

Table 1.8 *Annotated Exemplars on Specific Resources or Support Systems*

Participant	Responses	Observation
SHS 2	Cellphone po, sa TV, minsan sa ibang tao po na napapakinggan ko pong mag-English, sa mga matatandang naririnig ko po rito sa tindahan sa TV po.	SHS 2 uttered his responses with a calm tone of voice.

SHS 2 uttered his responses with a calm tone of voice. This implies that he is then positive with the question emphasizing the specific resources in learning the English language.

How do you feel teachers can better support students with E3L in the classroom?

Table 1.9 Annotated Exemplars on Teachers' Support for Students with E3L

Participant	Responses	Observation
SHS 3	Mas tulungan po na katulad po ng galing naming galing ng probinsya. Umpisahan po sana sa madadaling words at mabilis na mabigkas na mga salita.	SHS 3 answered his responses with an enthusiastic tone of voice.

SHS 3 answered his responses with an enthusiastic tone of voice. This implies that the participant is hopeful that indeed teachers can manage to help them with what he is experiencing with the E3L.

Looking ahead, what are some of your goals for improving your English language skills?

Table 1.10 Annotated Exemplars on Goals for Improving English Language Skills

Participant	Responses	Observation
SHS 1	Una rin po, yung pagbigkas ko po, dapat tama po ang sasabihin ko. Sunod po, confident po magsalita na mag-speak ng English. Dapat po marunong na po ako mag-English kaya nagbabasa po ako.	SHS 3 uttered her responses with calm facial expressions and tone of voice.

SHS 3 uttered her responses with calm facial expressions and tone of voice. This implies that the participant is optimistic that the challenges can still be turned to opportunities and development. She seems so willing to do it to achieve proficiency in using the E3L.

Corollary Question 2. What are the emerging themes based on the gathered data?

Can you tell me a bit about your language background? What languages do you speak at home and in your community?

Table 2.1 Provincial Dialect as Mother Tongue

Participants	Responses	Subordinate Themes
SHS 1	Ang una ko pong language ay Chavacano. Nu'ng bata pa po ako sa lugar namin, Zamboanga. Mas kinakasanayan ko po ang language namin dahil ito po ang gamit namin sa bahay, sa labas ng bahay. Sa loob ng school, Tagalog po ang gamit namin.	Chavacano
SHS 2	Sa amin po, sa probinsya, maano, hindi po Tagalog, ano po, Mindoreño sinasalita po namin sa Mindoro. Kapag ako nagkwentuhan po sa amin, mayroong iba ibang pananalita, mga ngani, baka, baga.	Mindoreño
SHS 3	Ang sinasalita po namin sa bahay at sa community po, ay Tagalog po, Marinduque Tagalog. Pero ang amin po ay matigas ang pagkakabanggit.	Marinduque Tagalog
SHS 4	Sa lugar po namin sa probinsya, Masbateño po. Ginagamit ko po iyon sa pakikipag-usap po sa bahay po, sa labas ng bahay. Tagalog po ang ginagamit namin sa school. Nag-Tagalog po ako rito po sa Laguna.	Masbateño

All of them answered their provincial dialect as their language spoken at home and community since this served as their foundation in communicating with people around them. These imply that since they were already in high school when they started learning to speak in Tagalog as their medium of communication, they were used and exposed to their mother tongue for a long time.

For learners in Mindanao, the results could be expected to be much worst since Filipino (also known as Tagalog) is not their first language (Skoropinski, 2013, as cited in Reyes, 2018). Gove and Cvelich (2011) reported that under such education, there were “stark regional differences, with a very small percentage of children unable to read in Filipino and English (1% and 2%, respectively) in Manila, compared with 24% and 30% of senior high school students in Mindanao” (p. 13). This suggests that for the country’s education system to truly help Filipino senior high school students to do better, curricular reforms that consider learners’ contexts such as their languages and language practices in teaching and learning have to be instituted.

While the past policies such as the BEP recognized the local (regional) languages as auxiliary media of instruction especially in Grades 1 and 2 (Department of Education, 1987), it did not thoroughly explore the pedagogical benefits of learners’ own languages since it focused more on English and Filipino. Incidentally, the succeeding language policies (i.e., 2009 Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education [MTB-MLE] and 2012 MTB-MLE) recognized the potential of learners’ mother tongues (MT). Both MTB-MLE policies emphasized the use of learners’ MT in instruction, and as both recognized the challenges to cater all MTs given that most classrooms are multilingual, they suggested the identification of a regional lingua franca or a language chosen by a majority of stakeholders. The 2009 MTB-MLE did not explicitly identify these languages; however, the 2012 MTB-MLE specified these languages—from eight languages identified as majority for having more than a million speakers, then to twelve, and finally to nineteen. Seemingly, the primary reason for the identification was the lack of necessary resources for all languages in a region.

How did you first start learning English? Can you describe your early experiences learning English?

Table 2.2 School and Home as English Language Environment

Participants	Responses	Subordinate Themes
SHS 1	Natuto na po ako talaga mag-English sa pagsasalita dito na po sa Laguna nu’ng Grade 10 po ako kasi karamihan po sa mga teachers po naming kailangan po naming mag-participate gamit ang English. Nag-eenglish po kami sa Zamboanga pero mas Tagalog po ang ginagamit namin sa pag-aaral.	School
SHS 2	Nu’ng una po, Grade 2 po, tapos ‘yung pinsan ko po magaling mag-English parang nainggit po ako sabay ginaya ko po ang pinsan ko sabay nag-aral ako paunti-unti. Sa school po, kapag ano po, ang ginagamit namin ay minsan Tagalog, minsan English.	School
SHS 3	Nu’ng bata po, kapag tinatanong ng magulang po, “What’s your name?”, “How old are you?”	Home
SHS 4	Nu’ng Grade 4 po pero nalilito pa po ako lalo na sa accent ng English.	School

Three among them answered school and another one was home. These imply that the school really served as the way of introducing English language to students, especially in provinces. They may also experience English words at home but when it comes to the technical usage of it both in written and oral communication, school plays a vital role.

As per Executive Order No. 210, Establishing the Policy to Strengthen the Use of the English Language as a Medium of Instruction in the Educational System, whereas, Section 7, Article XIV of the 1987 Constitution provides that for purposes of communication and instruction, the official languages of the Philippines are Filipino and, until otherwise provided by law, English. The following policies are hereby established:

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laboratory and/or experimental schools, and non-formal and vocational or technical educational institutions. As the primary medium of instruction, the percentage of time allotment for learning areas conducted in the English language is expected to be not less than seventy percent (70%) of the total time allotment for all learning areas in the secondary level.

What are some of the advantages of being an E3L student in the Philippines?

Table 2.3 *Multilingual Adaptability*

Participants	Responses	Subordinate Themes
SHS 1	May alam po akong salita sa tatlong lenggwahe po, pwede po rito at sa probinsya.	Multilingual adaptability
SHS 2	Pwede po ako makipag-usap sa probinsya at dito po sa Laguna.	Multilingual adaptability
SHS 3	Nakakaintindi po sa amin, pati po rito sa Laguna.	Multilingual adaptability
SHS 4	Kunwari po sa community, kaya ko po makaintindi po ng lenggwahe ng Masbate hindi tulad nila.	Multilingual adaptability

All of the senior high school students responded that being an E3L student in the Philippines was an advantage because they could be able to adapt easily compared to other E2L students. This implies that they still see their skills with three languages as a good way of connecting to people in a different place or province, like Laguna.

According to Harrow School (n.d) mentioned that learning a second or third language has many personal benefits too. Especially a young person. Knowledge of other languages allows senior high school students to understand and connect better with different cultures. This can lead to meaningful friendships and better professional relationships. Senior high school students become more open-minded and tolerant of one another.

What are some of the disadvantages of being an E3L student in the Philippines?

Table 2.4 *Language Barriers*

Participants	Responses	Subordinate Themes
SHS 1	Hindi po ako masyado marunong mag-English.	Inability to speak in English
	Kapag po may nag-English, natatakot po ako magsalita. Nahihiya po ako, baka po wrong grammar po ako, eh di pagtawanan po ako.	Fear of speaking English
SHS 2	Minsan hindi ako nakakasabay sa kanila dahil ang kanilang lenggwahe ay iba sa amin. Kaya nu'ng pinagbasa po ako nu'ng first semester, naiyak po dahil sa hiya. Kaya napaiyak po ako sa classroom.	Inability to communicate properly
SHS 3	Ma'am pag minsan naman po ay niloloko. Sasabihin po, Bisaya ka ba?	Different accent
SHS 4	'Yung ano po, pagma-master po nila ng wikang Tagalog. Kasi feeling ko po kabisado na nila hindi tulad ko.	Inability to speak in Filipino fluently

The senior high school students mentioned a lot of disadvantages that fall under language barriers such as inability and fear to speak in English, inability to communicate properly, different accent, and inability to speak in Filipino fluently. This implies that they really encountered problems in communication as Students with E3L. They lack ability to speak in English and Filipino languages that may result to fear and different accent.

As per Alberto (2016), the disadvantages of mother tongue impact on writing skills include difficulties in communicating with intended customers in international business letters due to negative transfer from the mother tongue. In the Philippines, issues faced by teachers in teaching mother tongue-based multilingual education include limited availability of audio materials for listening skills, teachers' limited vocabulary in the local dialect for speaking fluently, limited reading materials for teaching reading, and lack of resources to enhance writing skills

Have you ever felt embarrassed or discouraged when using English in the classroom? If so, can you tell me about an example?

Table 2.5 *Language Barriers*

Participants	Responses	Subordinate Themes
SHS 1	‘Pag ano po, kapag kinausap po ako ng kaklase ko ng English, hindi po ako makasagot, kasi hindi po ako masyado marunong.	Inability to speak in English
	Kapag nag-English po mga kaibigan ko, nag-uusap po kami, kapag ako na po ang magsasalita, magtatawanan po. Eh di ako po, minsan may doubt na po ako sa sarili ko, pinagtatawanan po ako, hindi ako kino-correct.	Doubtfulness in speaking English
SHS 2	Kapag ang aking kaklase ay nagsasalita ng English, minsan naiintindihan ko po ang sinasabi niya, minsan hindi. Hindi po kasi ako sanay. Kaya hindi ko po kaya, hindi ko po medyo ano nagegets.	Inability to understand English
	Nahiya po sa pagsasalita sa English, kapag po sa subject ng English, medyo nahihiya po ako magsalita.	Fear of speaking English
SHS 3	Nu’ng ano po, Grade 6. Parang mali mali po ang grammar ko sa stage, nakikita ko po sila na nagtatawanan, parang nakakainsulto po.	Fear of making grammatical errors
SHS 4	‘Yung pag-intindi po at pag-unawa. Kapag po nag-aano po, nag-rereport tapos English po ang gamit, minsan po nallito po ako sa mga salita po.	Doubtfulness in speaking English
	Tuwing po kapag feeling ko wrong grammar po. Nahihiya po ako, hindi ko na po inuulit, hindi na ako nag-eenglish. Nawawalan po ako ng confident.	Fear of making grammatical errors

All of the senior high school students mentioned the embarrassment or discouragement encountered in using the English language in the classroom which fall under language barriers. This implies all of them gained negative experiences in the classroom in using their third language, English, that make them feel doubtful and fearful at the same time in English communication.

Jugo (2020) emphasized that although the Philippines is still one of the preferred countries for foreign learners of English due to the affordability and quality of its English as Second Language Programs being offered, there is a worrying trend of decreasing English competence of teachers and learners. The English proficiency of the Filipino workforce has declined, which might be attributed to Filipino graduates having only English proficiency at the basic working proficiency level.

Numerous and varied studies have been conducted to determine the factors that affect English proficiency, particularly the language learning of nonnative English users. Evidence has shown that language anxiety is one of the strongest predictors of language learning success and that it has incapacitating effects on the language learner

[8, 9]. Whereas facilitating anxiety produces positive effects on the learners' performance, too much anxiety may cause poor performance.

How do you think factors like dialects, accents, and cultural backgrounds affect classroom communication for Students with E3L?

Table 2.6 *Negative Impact of Linguistic and Cultural Diversity*

Participants	Responses	Subordinate Themes
SHS 1	Syempre po galing po ako sa ibang lugar, parang nakasanayan ko pong magsalita ng Chavacano, 'pag punta ko po rito, nag-uatal utal po ako. Parang ano po, hindi po ako makapagsalita nang maayos gawa ng accent ko.	Stuttering
SHS 2	Kapag binully po ako sa classroom sabay ano ang bilis ko po mapaiyak kapag sinasabing hindi ako marunong mag-English. Sa pagsasalita ko po kasi, bulol po ganoon, mahirap pong magsalita.	Stuttering
SHS 3	Ma'am 'yung sa accent po, hindi po normal ang accent ko sa mga accent ng kausap ko po rito.	Different accent
SHS 4	'Yung tono ko po, kasi sa iba po parang 'yung ano po 'yung tono nila iba-iba. Parang nahihirapan po akong makasabay. Nahihirapan po akong makipag-usap.	Different tone

As per the participants, dialects, accents, and cultural backgrounds affected their classroom communication by having experiencing stuttering, different tone, and accent. This implies that their mother tongue, even not used in the room, is still manifested In the way they speak both Filipino and English. It affects the quality of their message as for the tone and accent.

Al-khreshah (2020) said that cultural background has a significant effect on their listening process. This study is expected to contribute markedly towards increasing the understanding of listening difficulties in language learning, and improving the teaching-learning process, by recommending effective remedies for addressing such challenges.

What strategies do you use to overcome challenges in understanding and using English in the classroom?

Table 2.7 *Adaptation of Language and Integration of Media*

Participants	Responses	Subordinate Themes
SHS 1	Kapag dating ko po sa room po, nakikita ko po ang mga kaklase ko. Sinasabi ko po sa sarili ko na dapat matuto rin ako mag-English para makasabay ako sa kanila.	Classmates as motivation in learning English
SHS 2	Minsan po, nanonood po ako ng mga movie ng English, medyo po natututo po ako, sa TikTok po na nakatranslate sa Tagalog para unti-unti po matuto.	English Movies TikTok
SHS 3	Tinanggap ko po, minsan po naghahanap na rin po sa dictionary kapag hindi familiar sa words. Minsan sa Facebook po, nakakakita ng mga words po.	Acceptance Dictionary
SHS 4	Pagtanggap po at pagtitiwala po sa sarili. Pag-practice po ng grammar sa English, spelling. Read and write po ang pag-practice.	Facebook Acceptance Confidence

The participants mentioned different strategies like classmates as motivation, acceptance, confidence and other platforms, and these fall under Adaptation of Language and Integration of Media. This implies that digital age is continuously developing that even the language learners are affected. Especially the young senior high school students nowadays, which are Gen Zs, they experience a lot of things using the power of media. With this, they see these platforms as ways of developing themselves that may affect their confidence, acceptance and motivation in using English in the classroom.

According to Alhassan (2022), the will and the ability to use the language depend on three factors: motivation, language anxiety, and attitude. Without these factors, long-term goals could hardly be accomplished. While motivation provides both the incentive to initiate learning and move on, language- anxiety is associated with a negative impact on the language learning.

As suggested by 5 Minute English (n.d.), an ESL instruction page, English is not just a language but a carrier of multiple cultures. For ESL learners, understanding the cultural underpinnings of language can be as challenging as learning the language itself so it is important to incorporate cultural elements into the curriculum. This can involve using literature, films, and other media from English-speaking countries. Encouraging discussions about these cultural elements helps senior high school students understand the context of the language they are learning.

Do you have any specific resources or support systems that help you learn English?

Table 2.8 *Integration of Media*

Participants	Responses	Subordinate Themes
SHS 1	Pag ano po, pag minsan po kapag nagawa po ako ng family letter, ginagamit ko pong pan-translate ang Google.	Google
SHS 2	Cellphone po, sa TV, minsan sa ibang tao po na napapakinggan ko pong mag-English, sa mga matatandang naririnig ko po rito sa tindahan sa TV po.	Cellphone Television
SHS 3	Dictionary po, Facebook po.	Dictionary
SHS 4	Gadget po, sa pagsesearch po ng mga ano words na pwede pong praktisin. Dictionary po, Google Translate.	Dictionary Google

The participants uttered various media as their sources in in using English. This implies that they are aware of their challenges that make them find ways to improve it using various media. With this, it is relevant to encourage them harness their media, information, and technology literacies so they can only gain those substantial pieces of information.

Widespread use of mobile and wireless devices in education has led to revolutionary changes in the way teachers teach and learners learn. Due to their pervasiveness, mobile phones are considered as being potentially valuable learning tools. Rahimi (2014) found out that mobile phones play in extending learning out of the classroom anywhere anytime.

How do you feel teachers can better support Students with E3L in the classroom?

Table 2.9 *Supportive and Inclusive Learning Environment*

Participants	Responses	Subordinate Themes
SHS 1	Base po sa pagututuro po sa amin sa PR 1, sinasabayan ko po ang bibig ng teacher po para sa pagbigkas ng English na salita po. Nakikinig po ako sa teacher tapos sinasabayan ko po. Natututo po ako sa English kapag nag-English po ang teacher, nasasabayan ko po.	Using English as medium of instruction

SHS 2	Ma'am ano, magsalita po ng English kapag po nagtuturo para matuto po paunti-unti, ma'am.	Using English as medium of instruction
SHS 3	Mas tulungan po na katulad po ng galing naming galing ng probinsya. Umpisahan po sana sa madadaling words at mabilis na mabigkas na mga salita.	Using easy-to-pronounce words
SHS 4	Pagsuporta po kagaya po ng pagtuturo ng English, ng mga language po na madaling maintindihan. Halimbawa po, nahihirapan po ako, tapos lalapit po ako sa inyo para magpatulong. Gumamit din po ng mga words n mabilis na maintindihan.	Giving support

The participants mentioned using English as medium of instruction, using easy-to-pronounce words, and giving support as the teacher's possible ways of helping them as Students with E3L. This implies that teachers really have to expose the senior high school students to English language so they can cope with the way it is used in communication. For them, it is also important to use easy words at the onset of their instruction so they can relate easily. They may experience complex situations in absorbing this language in the classroom that prompted them to come up with these ideas.

Teacher competences are vital to teaching English as a second language (L2) and English as a third language (L3) (Langeland, 2012, as cited in Alhassan, 2022). Teacher techniques in the current study are defined as the knowledge and competence needed by teachers to be successful in teaching English as L3 in secondary schools. These techniques include teaching vocabulary, teaching grammar, enhancing positive language attitudes (L-attitudes), reducing language anxiety (L- anxiety), helping senior high school students to develop writing and reading skills as well as collaborative teaching among others. There is no single document containing all the key and effective English teaching strategies, but rather an attempt to identify useful ones. Teaching strategies and teacher competencies are considered one of the backbones of effective and successful teaching (Kuyini et al., 2016, as cited in Alhassan, 2022).

Looking ahead, what are some of your goals for improving your English language skills?

Table 2.10 *Holistic Language Skill Development*

Participants	Responses	Subordinate Themes
SHS 1	Una rin po, yung pagbigkas ko po, dapat tama po ang sasabihin ko.	Pronunciation
	Sunod po, confident po magsalita na mag-speak ng English.	Confidence
	Dapat po marunong na po ako mag-English kaya nagbabasa po ako.	Reading
SHS 2	Ano po, magbasa ng mga English at mag-ano magpursigi sa pagsasalita ng English at 'yon ma'am.	Reading
SHS 3	Lagi pong magbasa ng English words.	Reading
	Tapos ma'am, pag hindi alam ang word, pakinggan sa Google ang tamang bigkas po.	Pronunciation
SHS 4	Ano po ma'am, kumaibigan po ng mga magagaling sa English para matuto ng English para maging better.	Responsible peers
	Matutong magsalita ng English sa pamamagitan ng practice. Pagtitiyaga po para mamaster ang pag-English po.	Practice

The participants mentioned various ways of language skill development which focused on pronunciation, reading, confidence, practice, and peers. With these, development of language is holistic. It does not only focus on the technicality of language, reading and pronunciation, but also to themselves as the speaker and their environment as well. Not only that, it is achieved only if it is practiced.

Bridgestock (2023) proposed various ways to improve English language skills. Three among these are the following: first, reading textbooks, articles and research publications is a critical part of any academic course. Improving one's reading skills will to succeed in your academic studies. Independent-level learners can practice reading quickly to find specific information in a text. Proficient-level learners can practice reading carefully to understand abstract concepts and academic arguments written in English.

Second, developing one's confidence when presenting or asking questions in seminars, by improving your English pronunciation. Independent-level learners can practice pronouncing different English sounds, such as long and short "i" sounds. Proficient-level learners can practice different word stresses and learn how this can change the meaning of a word or a sentence.

Third, practicing will prove that one has the right level of English and help one achieve their academic and professional goals.

Clustering Subordinate Themes to Superordinate Themes

Table 2.11 unveils the superordinate themes that were clustered from the Subordinate Themes. These were all accorded to the acquired lived experiences of the participants.

Table 2.11 *Clustering Subordinate Themes to Superordinate Themes*

Interview Questions	Subordinate Themes	Superordinate Themes
1. Can you tell me a bit about your language background? What languages do you speak at home and in your community?	1. Chavacano 2. Mindoreño 3. Marinduque Tagalog 4. Masbateño	1. Provincial Dialect as Mother Tongue
2. How did you first start learning English? Can you describe your early experiences learning English?	5. Home 6. School	2. School and Home as English Language Environment
3. What are some of the advantages of being an E3L student in the Philippines?	7. Multilingual adaptability	3. Multilingual adaptability
4. What are some of the disadvantages of being an E3L student in the Philippines?	8. Inability to speak in English 9. Fear of speaking English 10. Inability to communicate properly 11. Different accent 12. Inability to speak in Filipino fluently	4. Language Barriers
5. Have you ever felt embarrassed or discouraged when using English in the classroom? If so, can you tell me about an example?	13. Inability to speak in English 14. Doubtfulness in speaking English 15. Inability to understand English 16. Fear of speaking English 17. Fear of making grammatical errors	5. Language Barriers

6. How do you think factors like dialects, accents, and cultural backgrounds affect classroom communication for Students with E3L?	18. Stuttering 19. Different accent 20. Different tone	6. Negative Impact of Linguistic and Cultural Diversity
7. What strategies do you use to overcome challenges in understanding and using English in the classroom?	21. Peer support 22. English Movies 23. TikTok 24. Acceptance 25. Dictionary 26. Facebook 27. Confidence	7. Adaptation of Language and Integration of Media
8. Do you have any specific resources or support systems that help you learn English?	28. Google 29. Cellphone 30. Television 31. Dictionary	8. Integration of Media
9. How do you feel teachers can better support Students with E3L in the classroom?	32. Using English as medium of instruction 33. Using easy-to-pronounce words 34. Giving support	9. Supportive and Inclusive Learning Environment
10. Looking ahead, what are some of your goals for improving your English language skills?	35. Pronunciation 36. Confidence 37. Reading 38. Peer support 39. Practice	10. Holistic Language Skill Development

This table shows that based on the gathered responses, there 39 subordinate themes and 10 superordinate themes emerged.

Clustering Superordinate Themes to Main Themes

Table 12 shows the clustering of superordinate themes to main themes. These were all from the lived experiences of senior high school students with English as their third language.

Table 2.12 Clustering Superordinate Themes to Main Themes

Main Theme 1: Primary Language and Communication Environment Provincial Dialect as Mother Tongue School and Home as English Language Environment Multilingual Adaptability
Main Theme 2: Negative Effects of Mother Tongue Language Barriers Negative Impact of Linguistic and Cultural Diversity
Main Theme 3: Adaptation and Integration of Media Adaptation of Language and Integration of Media Integration of Media
Main Theme 4: Supportive Learning Environment Supportive and Inclusive Learning Environment Main Theme 5: Language Skill Development Holistic Language Skill Development

This table shows the main themes that emerged from all the responses of the participants. These are (1) Primary Language and Communication Environment, (2) Negative Effects of Mother Tongue, (3) Adaptation and Integration of Media, (4) Supportive Learning Environment, and (5) Holistic Language Skill Development.

Corollary Question 3. Based on the findings of the study, what Holistic Language Skill Development Plan may be proposed?

Table 3 Holistic Language Skill Development Plan

Stakeholder / Audience	Activity	Products	Timeline
School Head/Principal	Develop and Implement English and Filipino Programs	- Curriculum plans for English and Filipino programs - Budget allocation for program resources	Yearly
Advisers	Integrate Language Learning Activities into Home Room Guidance	- Lesson plans incorporating language skills development - Student presentations or projects in Filipino and English	Weekly
Teachers	Use Filipino and English as Mediums of Instruction	- Lesson plans delivered in Filipino and English (with translanguaging strategies) - Student assessments demonstrating proficiency	Daily for each class
Parents	Facilitate Home Support for Filipino and English Use	- Communication materials for parents on language learning strategies - Collaborative activities for students and parents in Filipino and English	Ongoing (e.g., monthly workshops, weekly communication)

This table shows the researcher’s crafted Holistic Language Skill Development Plan which incorporates: (1) English and Filipino Programs that ensures dedicated focus on developing proficiency in both languages; (2) Integration of Language Education in Home Room Guidance that fosters language learning beyond traditional classroom settings; (3) Utilization of English and Filipino language and Translanguaging that promotes immersive language acquisition; (4) Emphasis on Easy-to-pronounce Words that minimizes confusion and facilitates smoother language acquisition; and (5) Home Support for the Senior High School Students that encourages Filipino and English language use within the home environment.

CONCLUSION

Main Theme 1: Primary Language and Communication Environment

That the senior high school students use their mother tongue in their home and community. They are not exposed to English and Filipino but as they grow older, they learn how to use it in their school which is slightly introduced at home. Nevertheless, they still see their skills with three languages as a good way of connecting to people in a different place or province, like Laguna.

Main Theme 2: Negative Effects of Mother Tongue

That the senior high school students encounter problems in communication as Students with E3L. They lack ability to speak in English and Filipino languages that may result to fear and different accent. Since they gained negative experiences in the classroom in using their third language, English, make them feel doubtful and fearful at the same time in English communication. Also, their mother tongue, even not used in the room, is still manifested in the way they speak both Filipino and English. It affects the quality of their message as for the tone and accent.

Main Theme 3: Adaptation and Integration of Media

That digital age is continuously developing that even the language learners are affected. Especially the young senior high school students nowadays, which are Gen Zs, they experience a lot of things using the power of media. With this, they see these platforms as ways of developing themselves that may affect their confidence, acceptance and motivation in using English in the classroom. They are aware of their challenges that make them find ways to improve it using various media. With this, it is relevant to encourage them harness their media, information, and technology literacies so they can only gain those substantial pieces of information.

Main Theme 4: Supportive Learning Environment

That teachers really have to expose the senior high school students to English language so they can cope with the way it is used in communication which for them serve as supportive learning environment. It is also important to use easy words at the onset of their instruction so they can relate easily. They may experience complex situations in absorbing this language in the classroom that prompted them to come up with these ideas.

Main Theme 5: Language Skill Development

That the development of language is holistic. It does not only focus on the technicality of language, reading and pronunciation, but also to themselves as the speaker and their environment as well. Not only that, it is achieved only if it is practiced.

Recommendations***Main Theme 1: Primary Language and Communication Environment***

Senior high school students may still use their mother tongue following the DO 16, S. 2012, Implementation of the Mother Tongue-Based- Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE), but at the same time, the parents or home may still also be there to guide them in introducing their second and third languages, Filipino and English.

Main Theme 2: Negative Effects of Mother Tongue

Senior high school students may be exposed to Filipino and English not only in schools but also at home to avoid negative effects of mother tongue that lead them experience challenges in communication.

Accordingly, teachers may also help the students to be exposed to English and Filipino languages since it is also mandated by the Department of Education.

Main Theme 3: Adaptation and Integration of Media

Senior high school students may use media as their way of achieving proficiency in both languages, Filipino and English. However, it is also important to apply media, information and technology literacies in utilizing different forms of media to ensure the effectiveness and accuracy of learning.

Main Theme 4: Supportive Learning Environment

Language teachers may continue using inclusive and supporting language strategies to further boost the confidence of students with E3L such as open communication, various activities using simple to complex words, words of affirmation, and others.

Main Theme 5: Language Skill Development

School stakeholders may continue the conduct of Catch-up Fridays for these hone the students' language skills both in English and Filipino. It is just that, these may not only focus on specific learning materials but students themselves may choose the resources they want to use for as long as these resources are free from inappropriate content and information. With this, they may enjoy reading and gain more confidence in using and absorbing English and Filipino languages not only with themselves but also with their classmates. Aside from that, they may conduct culminating activities that may encourage learners to perform using these languages to further improve their confidence in speaking.

Specifically, they may consider utilizing the Holistic Language Skill Development Plan which incorporates: (1) English and Filipino Programs that ensures dedicated focus on developing proficiency in both languages; (2) Integration of Language Education in Home Room Guidance that fosters language learning beyond traditional classroom settings; (3) Utilization of English and Filipino language and Translanguaging that promotes immersive language acquisition; (4) Emphasis on Easy-to-pronounce Words that minimizes confusion and facilitates smoother language acquisition; and (5) Home Support for the Senior High School Students that encourages Filipino and English language use within the home environment.

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